

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**CHRONIC NICHE INFLAMMATION IN ENDOMETRIOSIS-
ASSOCIATED INFERTILITY: CURRENT UNDERSTANDING
AND FUTURE THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES.****¹Dr Syeda Umal Baneen,²Dr Nida Zeb Abbasi,³Dr Aroosa Sultan**^{1,2}MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.³MBBS, Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

It is defined as the formation of endometrial tissue outside the urine cavity in estrogen-dependent inflammation condition is known as endometriosis that affects 10% of females at childbearing age and contributes up to 50% cases of infertility. It has an awful association with assisted reproductive technology inclusive low implantation and pregnancy rates. To treat infertility originated with endometriosis required a deep understanding of its pathology. In this article we have discussed the chronic niche inflammation in endometriosis development, targeting inflammation for treatment of endometriosis-associated infertility, and stem cell therapy. Moreover, mesenchymal stem cell-based treatments are highlighted as potential endometriosis therapy.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Syeda Umal Baneen,**

MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Syeda Umal Baneen et al, **Chronic Niche Inflammation In Endometriosis-Associated Infertility: Current Understanding And Future Therapeutic Strategies.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

It is defined as the formation of endometrial tissue outside the uterine cavity in estrogen dependent inflammation condition is known as endometriosis. Approximately, 5-10% of females at childbearing, 80% experienced pelvic pain, and 21-50% of females with infertile. Endometriosis is associated with more complications such as pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, menorrhagia, dyspareunia, and dyschezia. Affected females are at greater risk to develop ovarian cancer and endometrial cancer, patients are more prone to cardiovascular disease, autoimmune, and allergic diseases.¹ However, to relief the pain and treatment of infertility is the main objective of current therapy of endometriosis. The treatment of suspected patients proceeded through empirical therapy using inflammatory drugs, gonadotrophin-releasing hormone agonists, progestogens, and hormonal contraceptive, instead of diagnosis based on presented symptoms of endometriosis.³ Thereafter, if empirical treatment shows inadequate response, laparoscopic exploration, and excision will be considered as curative treatment.² Interestingly, the emergence of conventional medical treatment has an abundant role to cure endometriosis-associated infertility using the assisted reproductive technology but it is illustrated that pretreatment with gonadotrophin-releasing hormone agonists can ameliorate the pregnancy rate 4-folds. Medical therapies are very effective in the reduction of pain in patients of endometriosis, on the other hand, medical or hormonal treatments are insufficient to treat infertility in patients with endometriosis. Thus, these treatments subdue the ovarian function and develop the contraceptive condition.⁴

Moreover, it is difficult to understand all the causes of endometriosis that impaired the normal reproduction organ in women while distorted pelvic anatomy due to adhesions, ovarian dysfunction, abnormal peritoneal function, and impaired endometrial receptivity are the various causes that have been explored by researchers.⁵ Here, we will discuss the dysregulated niche immune modulation and focused on therapies helpful in the reduction of infertility faced by endometriosis patients.

Chronic Niche Inflammation in Endometriosis Development

The chronic niche inflammation was specifically found in the peritoneal cavity, ovaries, and uterus.

i. Peritoneal Cavity

The abnormality in the peritoneal cavity due to chronic inflammation may lead to developing infertility in

patients with endometriosis. The amount of peritoneal fluid was greater in patients with endometriosis than the normal fertile women. Endometriosis bring changes in the immune system such as inhibit the T-cells mediated cytotoxicity to endometrial cells, reduced the activity of natural killer cells, and escalate the activated macrophages.⁶ These alterations assist the endometriotic implants to survive by providing the suitable immune-tolerant microenvironment. The specific secretions were secreted by the endometriotic implants including estradiol, progesterone, vascular endothelial growth factor, and many other factors that promote the endometriosis development.⁷

ii. Ovaries

The alteration of ovarian function through the local effect in case of endometriomas. Endometrioma contain cystic fluid is an ample source of pro-inflammatory cytokines, growth factors (TGF- β , and matrix metalloproteases) and reactive oxygen species. This fluid can diffuse to surrounding tissue and impose a bad effect on the function of the adjacent ovary.⁸ The structural changes were observed in the surrounding tissue of ovarian endometriomas such as impaired follicular density, higher fibrosis, and reduction in the cortex-specific stroma. Local inflammatory reaction in endometriomas ovarian cortex enhanced the oxidative stress, growth factor, and reactive oxygen species encourage fibrosis and profibrotic gene expression of plasminogen activator inhibitor-1. Alteration of the structure is the reason for ovarian stroma loss and impose the deleterious effects on folliculogenesis as a repercussion of this reduction of blood supply to follicles and lowering the number of growth factors secreted through the stroma cells.⁹

iii. Uterus

Various clinical publications identified the reduction rate of implantation during in vitro fertilization in patients with endometriosis and 26 studies based on meta-analysis illustrated that substantial reduction of implantation numbers and lowering the clinical pregnancy rate in patients with acute endometriosis.¹¹ In a prospective study without considering the factors involved in oocyte and embryo quality demonstrated that patients with endometriosis were found with lesser implantation pregnancy rates than control group patients.¹⁰ There was no difference in reproduction rate was found for females of the age group of 35 to 40 years while it is elusive to figure out the exact percentage of effects of endometriosis on implantation.¹¹

Targeting Inflammation for Treatment of Endometriosis-Associated Infertility

i. Immunomodulators

In a study of the animal model demonstrated that pentoxifylline decrease endometriotic lesion and meliorate the fertilization process but lack of evidence was found which support the use of pentoxifylline for infertility in women with endometriosis.¹³ Lufunomide and Loxoribine are also immunomodulators, decrease the size of the endometriotic implants with the enhancement of dendritic cells, and lowering the number of natural killer cells. In preclinical studies, limited development of endometriosis lesion was identified with the use of drugs namely rosiglitazone and pioglitazone which were previously used in diabetes treatment as insulin sensitizer.¹⁴

ii. Anticytokine Treatment

Proinflammatory cytokines are amply found in peritoneal fluid. A study shows the decrease of formation of an inflammatory cytokine through the inhibition of tumor necrosis factor (TNF) α -mediated pathways. Although controversy was a notice in studies for the use of anti-TNF- α treatment to ameliorate the pain induced by endometriosis. Currently, clinical pregnancy and birth rate has been increased in patients of endometriosis treatment with anti-TNF- α along with assisted reproductive technology (ART).¹⁵ Tocilizumab based therapy significantly reduced the lesion size of endometriosis and targeted delivery of anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-4 diminish the ectopic lesion formation.¹⁶

iii. Statins

Statins used as inhibitors of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme-A (HMG-CoA) reductase. The various study attempted that statins decline the chemokine production which lower the immune cell migration and adhesion, also decrease the activated T-cells by changing the lipid raft and dwindle the major histocompatibility complex molecules. A clinical therapy demonstrated that statins also exhibited anti-inflammatory effects.¹⁷

Cell-Based Therapy for Endometriosis Treatment Stem Cells in Endometriosis Pathogenesis

The research on stem cells present in the endometrium is feasible because endometrial tissue has the potential to regenerate during each menstrual cycle. Researchers stated that there is a relationship between adult stem cells and endometriosis development. The endometrial stem cell is recognized as clonogenic cells in human endometria.¹⁸ The segregation of endometrial mesenchymal stem cells can be achieved with the use of different markers such as PDGFR β and SUSD2. Results of many studies show that endometrial mesenchymal stem cells have a greater involvement for octamer-binding transcription

factor 4 (OCT4) with an effective response to niche cytokines ultimately impose healthy control to endometrial tissues.¹⁹ Stem cell therapy has been used for the treatment of infertility specifically Asherman's syndrome elucidated by endometrium adhesion and fibrosis in patients with infection or absence of menstruation.²⁰ The key point of stem cell treatment is to decrease the inflammation after adhesiolysis. In an animal-based model study, stem cell transplantation ameliorates ovarian function especially in premature ovarian insufficiency, reducing the apoptosis of granulosa cells with modulation of cytokine expression.²¹

DISCUSSION:

The study of menopause women with a history of endometriosis revealed that 43 patients of age range from 35 to 60 years, 40 patients had a history of endometriosis which was confirmed through the laparoscopic excision and presented symptoms of menorrhagia, infertility pelvic pain while 3 patients had not diagnosed with premenopausal endometriosis history. 36 patients undergo to surgical therapy.³

In another study patients of age range 48 to 55 presenting the symptoms such as mid-right side lower abdominal pain, urinary frequency, constipation for two months and having a medical history of pelvic endometriosis, left ovarian endometriosis, adenomyosis, and surgical menopause, clearly diagnosed with carcinomas cell in endometriosis of the retro-peritoneum had treated through the surgery and 22 months of radiation therapy.²²

A study on patients of the age group of 60, 57, and 54 years were suffering from the right side abdominal pain for four years and experienced the cramp-like discomfort in the abdomen and postmenopausal bleeding, diagnosed with widespread endometriosis in the ovary and clinician offered the surgery along with aromatase inhibitors and surgery plus chemotherapy.²³

CONCLUSIONS:

Long and last medical care of endometriosis patients mainly focused to overcome the pain, symptoms, and improve the quality of life. According to an estimation, almost 5 to 59% of patients face inadequate treatment, and 17-35% of patients suffered from recurring symptoms after a few months of treatment. Therefore, novel strategies being targeting the dysregulated immune system that distinguishes the endometriosis but not proven to be effective to use in standard management. Cell-based therapy provided an option to address the issues of endometriosis linked

with infertility due to its immunomodulatory response. This method is effectively used in the diagnosis of Asherman's syndrome and premature ovarian failure

REFERENCES:

1. Carter, J.E. Combined hysteroscopic and laparoscopic findings in patients with chronic pelvic pain. *J. Am. Assoc. Gynecol. Laparosc.* 1994, 2, 43–47.
2. Bedaiwy, M.A.; Allaire, C.; Yong, P.; Alfaraj, S. Medical management of endometriosis in patients with chronic pelvic pain. *Semin. Reprod. Med.* 2017, 35, 38–53.
3. Johnson, N.P.; Hummelshoj, L.; World Endometriosis Society Montpellier Consortium. Consensus on current management of endometriosis. *Hum. Reprod.* 2013, 28, 1552–1568.
4. Sallam, H.N.; Garcia-Velasco, J.A.; Dias, S.; Arici, A.; Abou-Setta, A.M. Long-term pituitary down-regulation before in vitro fertilization (IVF) for women with endometriosis. *Cochrane Database Syst. Rev.* 2006, 1, CD004635.
5. De Ziegler, D.; Borghese, B.; Chapron, C. Endometriosis and infertility: Pathophysiology and management. *Lancet* 2010, 376, 730–738.
6. Jeung, I.; Cheon, K.; Kim, M.R. Decreased cytotoxicity of peripheral and peritoneal natural killer cell in endometriosis. *Biomed Res. Int.* 2016, 2016, 2916070.
7. Králíčková, M.; Vetvicka, V. Immunological aspects of endometriosis: A review. *Ann. Transl. Med.* 2015, 3, 153.
8. Sanchez, A.M.; Vigano, P.; Somigliana, E.; Panina-Bordignon, P.; Vercellini, P.; Candiani, M. The distinguishing cellular and molecular features of the endometriotic ovarian cyst: From pathophysiology to the potential endometrioma-mediated damage to the ovary. *Hum. Reprod. Update* 2014, 20, 217–230.
9. Hsueh, A.J.; Kawamura, K.; Cheng, Y.; Fauser, B.C. Intraovarian control of early folliculogenesis. *Endocr. Rev.* 2015, 36, 1–24.
10. Prapas, Y.; Goudakou, M.; Matalliotakis, I.; Kalogeraki, A.; Matalliotaki, C.; Panagiotidis, Y.; Ravanos, K.; Prapas, N. History of endometriosis may adversely affect the outcome in menopausal recipients of sibling oocytes. *Reprod. Biomed. Online* 2012, 25, 543–548.
11. Harb, H.M.; Gallos, I.D.; Chu, J.; Harb, M.; Coomarasamy, A. The effect of endometriosis on in vitro fertilisation outcome: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BJOG* 2013, 120, 1308–1320.
12. González-Comadran, M.; Schwarze, J.E.; Zegers-Hochschild, F.; Souza, M.D.; Carreras, R.; Checa, M.A. The impact of endometriosis on the outcome of assisted reproductive technology. *Reprod. Biol. Endocrinol.* 2017, 15, 8.
13. Steinleitner, A.; Lambert, H.; Suarez, M.; Serpa, N.; Roy, S. Immunomodulation in the treatment of endometriosis-associated subfertility: Use of pentoxifylline to reverse the inhibition of fertilization by surgically induced endometriosis in a rodent model. *Fertil. Steril.* 1991, 56, 975–979.
14. Kim, C.H.; Lee, Y.J.; Kim, J.B.; Lee, K.H.; Kwon, S.K.; Ahn, J.W.; Kim, S.H.; Chae, H.D.; Kang, B.M. Effect of pioglitazone on production of regulated upon activation normal T-cell expressed and secreted (RANTES) and IVF outcomes in infertile women with endometriosis. *Dev. Reprod.* 2013, 17, 207–213.
15. Barcz, E.; Milewski, L.; Dziunycz, P.; Kamiński, P.; Płoski, R.; Malejczyk, J. Peritoneal cytokines and adhesion formation in endometriosis: An inverse association with vascular endothelial growth factor concentration. *Fertil. Steril.* 2012, 97, 1380–1386.
16. Quattrone, F.; Sanchez, A.M.; Pannese, M.; Hemmerle, T.; Vigano, P.; Candiani, M.; Petraglia, F.; Neri, D.; Panina-Bordignon, P. The targeted delivery of interleukin 4 inhibits development of endometriotic lesions in a mouse model. *Reprod. Sci.* 2015, 22, 1143–1152.
17. Jain, M.K.; Ridker, P.M. Anti-inflammatory effects of statins: Clinical evidence and basic mechanisms. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 2005, 4, 977–987.
18. Kao, A.P.; Wang, K.H.; Chang, C.C.; Lee, J.N.; Long, C.Y.; Chen, H.S.; Tsai, C.F.; Hsieh, T.H.; Tsai, E.M. Comparative study of human eutopic and ectopic endometrial mesenchymal stem cells and the development of an in vivo endometriotic invasion model. *Fertil. Steril.* 2011, 95, 1308–1315.
19. Yerlikaya, G.; Balendran, S.; Pröstling, K.; Reischer, T.; Birner, P.; Wenzl, R.; Kuessel, L.; Streubel, B.; Husslein, H. Comprehensive study of angiogenic factors in women with endometriosis compared to women without endometriosis. *Eur. J. Obstet. Gynecol. Reprod. Biol.* 2016, 204, 88–98.
20. Li, X.; Bai, J.; Ji, X.; Li, R.; Xuan, Y.; Wang, Y. Comprehensive characterization of four different populations of human mesenchymal stem cells as regards their immune properties, proliferation and

- differentiation. *Int. J. Mol. Med.* 2014, 34, 695–704.
21. Ozcan Cenksoy, P.; Oktem, M.; Erdem, O.; Karakaya, C.; Cenksoy, C.; Erdem, A.; Guner, H.; Karabacak, O. A potential novel treatment strategy: Inhibition of angiogenesis and inflammation by resveratrol for regression of endometriosis in an experimental rat model. *Gynecol. Endocrinol.* 2015, 31, 219–224.
 22. Brooks JJ, Wheeler JE. Malignancy arising in extragonadal endometriosis: a case report and summary of the world literature. *Cancer* 1977;40:3065–3073.
 23. Joseph J, Reed CE, Sahn SA. Thoracic endometriosis. Recurrence following hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy and successful treatment with talc pleurodesis. *Chest* 1994;106:1894–1896.
 24. Karanjgaokar VC, Murphy DJ, Samra JS, Mann CH. Malignant transformation of residual endometriosis after hysterectomy: a case series. *Fertil Steril* 2009;92: 2037.e2019–2021.